

ENHANCING NURSING MANAGER'S KNOWLEDGE REGARDING ORGANIZATIONAL EXCELLENCE EDUCATIONAL PROGRAM

Dima B. M. EIFeky ¹, Gehan M. A. Mostafa ² and Dalal T. Akel ³

¹ B.Sc. Nursing, Faculty of Nursing, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt.

² Professor, Nursing Administration, Faculty of Nursing, Helwan University, Cairo, Egypt.

³ Professor, Nursing Administration, Faculty of Nursing, Ain Shams University, Cairo, Egypt.

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Abstract

Introduction: Organizational excellence refers to the focus on an organization to establish a standard set of organizational elements that together deliver outstanding results. Researcher explored the relationship between organizational excellence and organizational performance, researchers found such a relationship positive, and that organizational excellence helps managers recognize their organizations more. **Aim:** The study aimed to enhance nursing managers knowledge regarding organizational excellence educational program. **Setting:** The study was conducted at Dar El-Shefa Hospital. **Design:** A quasi experimental research design will be used in this study. **Subject:** A purposive sample of nurse managers was included (N=40). **Tools:** Self-administrated questionnaire sheets to assess demographic characteristics of nursing mangers and organizational excellence questionnaire of nursing managers apply before, after and follow up implementing organizational excellence training sessions. **Results:** The organizational excellence program had a large positive effect size on total knowledge during pre, post & three months follow up. **Conclusion:** Nursing managers knowledge regarding organizational excellence has improved after conducting an education program. **Recommendation:** This study recommended to achieve an organizational excellence, every employee must understand not only the company's vision, but also know their own roles, responsibilities and the specific actions they need to take in order to help achieve this vision.

Keywords: Competences, Excellence, Managerial, Nurse mangers and Organizational

INTRODUCTION

Healthcare is multifaceted and faced with several challenges including inadequate staffing and increasing workloads. As the largest health care group, nurses are mostly at the center of these challenges. To deal with these clinical challenges that confront healthcare delivery, it is crucial for the nurse manager (NM) to be a primary successful driver for organizational excellence and possess the relevant critical managerial competencies for the effective management of the scarce resources in order to address these clinical challenges that face healthcare delivery (*Dawabsheh et al., 2019*).

Excellent organizations proactively and systematically take action to ensure that they have the human resource capability to meet their current and future work requirements; these organizations have made talent management practice critical force in their drive for excellence. Organizational excellence is defined as the ongoing efforts to establish an internal framework of standards and processes intended to engage and motivate employees to deliver products and services that fulfill customer requirements within business expectations. It is the achievement by an organization of consistent superior performance, for example, outputs that exceed meeting objectives, needs, or expectations (*Hamouda & Abd El-Aliem, 2020*).

Managers cannot succeed and become more effective in today's global business climate unless they have the abilities that are genuinely matched with the demands of

that environment. The variety and diversity of firms' workforces have raised the need for managers to reskill and upskill their capabilities. To effectively achieve their missions and be more successful in such a global environment, the organizations need to recruit people with skills and competencies that better match organizational requirements and work on developing their top-management skills to be more effective (*Suliman, 2021*).

Significance of the Study

Organizational excellence has several main principles, such as emphasis on performance and customer satisfaction, leadership and specific priorities, process and fact management, employee growth and involvement, learning, innovation and creativity, researcher explored the relationship between organizational excellence and organizational performance. Researchers found such a relationship positive, and that organizational excellence helps managers recognize their organizations more (*Saleh et al., 2016*). Some studies indicate that about (65%) of the variance in organizational productivity is explained by excellence principles, excellence practices (*Saeed et al., 2018*).

AIM OF THE STUDY

The aim of this study is to enhancing nursing managers knowledge regarding organizational excellence educational program:

Research hypothesis

The organizational excellence program will be enhancing knowledge of nursing managers organizational excellence.

Subjects and Methods:

I. Technical item

The technical item includes research design, setting, subject and tools for data collection.

RESEARCH DESIGN

Quasi experimental research design was used in this study.

Setting:

The study was conducted at Dar El-Shefa hospital, the hospital is consisted of one building; consists of basement, ground floor and six floors and the hospital had a bed capacity more than 160 beds include many specialties.

Subjects:

All available nurse managers were included during data collection.

Tools of Data Collection:

Tool: Self-Administered Questionnaire sheet for organizational excellence:

A self – administrated questionnaire will be modified by researcher after the reviewing the literature based on *Araya, et al., (2019)*. It will consist of the following two parts to collect the required data from nurse managers.

Part 1: Personal characteristic data for nursing managers: such as (Age, gender, educational qualification, years of experience, etc.,).

Part 2: Organizational excellence questionnaire: will be conducted by the researcher to assess nursing managers knowledge about organizational excellence through program. It consists of the following seven components: Leadership (5 items), policy and strategy (5 items), nurses (6 items), partnerships and resources (5 items), processes (6 items) and patient (5 items).

The item response categories include :1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Neutral, 4=Agree and 5=Strongly Agree.

Scoring system: This tool consisted of 32 items with a total grade (160). This instrument uses a 5-point Likert scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 strongly agree. The grades for each item were summed up and then converted into a percent score.

- **Satisfactory level: $\geq 60\%$.**
- **Unsatisfactory level: $< 60\%$.**

Validity of the tools:

Validity of the tools was done namely face validity and content validity. The tools were translated into Arabic and tested by a group of five experts specialized in nursing administration from different three universities; Ain Shams University, Menoufia University and Helwan University through an opinionative sheet to measure validity of the tools and the necessary modifications was been done accordingly.

Face Validity

Face validity was conducted based on five expert's opinions which were regarding the tool's layout, format and clarity of parts.

Content Validity

Content validity was done to determine the appropriateness of each item to be included in the questionnaire sheet. Necessary modifications were done based on five expert recommendations.

Reliability of the tools:

Reliability for the utilized tools was tested to determine the extent to which the items of the tools are inter-correlated to each other. The Cronbach's alpha model is one of the most popular reliability statistics in use today and considered as a model of internal consistency that used to estimate of reliability of test scores. Reliability of Organizational excellence questionnaire for nursing managers by Cronbach's alpha was (0.976) respectively. While Reliability of Managerial competencies questionnaire for nursing managers by Cronbach's alpha test was (0.967) respectively.

Pilot study:

The pilot study was carried out on (10%) of the total sample size (4 nursing managers) to test applicability and clarity of tools and time needed to complete it. Total time needed to complete tool was ranged between (10:20) minutes. No modifications were done so participants in the pilot study were included in the study sample.

Ethical considerations:

The research approval was obtained from Faculty of Nursing ethical committee of Helwan University before starting the study, an approval was obtained from the director of Dar Al-Shifa Hospital. Informed consent was sought and obtained from each participating subject prior to data collection, they were informed about the purpose and expected outcomes of the study and that the study is harmless and their participation is voluntary and they have the right to withdrawal from the study at any time without reason. They also were assured that, anonymity and confidentiality will be guaranteed, as well as gathered data will be used for the research purpose only. Ethics, values, culture and believes will respected.

II. Operational design

The operational design includes: preparatory phase, pilot study and field work.

A) The preparatory phase:

It was included reviewing of past, current, national and international related literature and theoretical knowledge of various aspects of the study using books, articles, internet, periodicals and journals.

B) Field Work:

The field work started actually at the beginning of April 2022 to October 2022. The researcher met the hospital manager to explain the aim of the study to gain their approval on data collection. The researcher collected data by herself through meeting nursing

managers and explaining the purpose of the study to them in the study setting and this done in collaboration with training department. The researcher was present at all time during fulfilling the questionnaire forms to answer any questions. The time needed by nursing managers to complete tool (organizational excellence) was ranged between (10-20) minutes. Also, the researcher checked the completeness of each filled sheet to ensure the absence of any missing data.

III. Administrative Design

Approval to carry out this study was obtained from the Dean of the Faculty of Nursing Helwan University and Director of Dar Al-shifa Hospital to conduct the study. Individual oral consent was also obtained from each nursing manager to participate in the study

IV. Statistical design

Data entry and analysis were performed using SPSS statistical package version 25. Categorical variables were expressed as number and percentage while continuous variables were expressed as (mean \pm SD). Chi-Square (χ^2) was used to test the association between row and column variable of qualitative data.

The Shapiro Wilk tests has a significance value below 0.05, indicating that the data did not follow a normal distribution; therefore, nonparametric tests were used for analysis.

ANOVA test was used to compare mean in normally distributed quantitative variables in more than two groups. The Kruskal–Wallis test are nonparametric tests used to compare the mean ranks of scores and determine significant differences in mean

values for more than 2 groups. Pearson correlation was done to measure correlation between quantitative variables.

For all tests, a two-tailed p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant, P-value ≤ 0.01 was considered highly statistically significant. While p-value > 0.05 was considered not significant.

RESULTS

Table 1: Personal characteristics among the studied nursing managers (n=40)

Nursing manager's characteristics		N	%
▪ Age (in years)	≤ 25	1	2.5
	$\geq 26- \leq 30$	11	27.5
	$\geq 31- \leq 40$	5	12.5
	≥ 41 years	23	57.5
$\bar{x} + SD$	37.32 + 6.81		
▪ Gender	Male	1	2.5
	Female	39	97.5
Ratio	M to F ratio=1: 39		
▪ Education	Bachelor's degree	23	57.5
	other	8	20.0
	Master's degree	9	22.5
▪ Job title	Director	5	12.5
	Head nurse	26	65.0
	Supervisor	9	22.5
▪ Year of experience	< 5 years	2	5.0
	≥ 5 years ≤ 10 years	14	35.0
	≥ 11 years	24	60.0
$\bar{x} + SD$	16.82 + 6.6		
▪ Total tenure time as nurse manager	< 5 years	11	27.5
	≥ 5 years ≤ 10 years	12	30.0
	≥ 11 years	17	42.5
$\bar{x} + SD$	9.80 + 5.69		

Significant $p \leq 0.05$ **Highly significant $p \leq 0.01$

- **Table (1)** Show, that More than half of study nursing managers (57,5%) their age was ≥ 41 years old with a mean score and standard deviation (37.32 + 6.81). Also, majority of them were females (97.5%), More than half of them (57.5%) were holding a bachelor's nursing degrees. As concerning the job title, more than half of them (65%) were a head nurse. As considering, year of experience, about sixty percentage (60%) of them were worked ≥ 11 years.

Figure 1: percentage distribution of total knowledge regarding organizational excellent during pre, post & three months follow up among the studied nursing managers (n=40)

$\chi^2=54.3, P=0.000$

Figure (1) Denotes, during the pre-test the studied nursing managers gained seventeen and half percentage (17.5%). As compared with the phase of post-test phase nursing managers gained satisfactory level of knowledge regarding organizational excellent with the eighty-seven and half percentage (87.5%) of followed by the phase of follow-up test eighty-five percentage (85%). In addition to presence of difference between observed and expected values with a significant statistical difference at $\chi^2=54.3, P=0.000$.

Table 2: means score of nursing managers according to their total satisfaction regarding organizational excellence (n=40)

variables	Pre (mean +SD)	Post (mean +SD)	Follow up (mean +SD)
Leadership	12.38+ 2.75	19.40 + 3.6	18.37 + 3.88
Policy and strategy	11.90 + 3.02	19.45 + 3.45	18.35 + 3.81
Nurses	14.33 + 3.41	23.35 + 4.09	21.97 + 4.52
Partnerships	11.77 + 2.98	19.38 + 3.66	18.45 + 3.76
Processes	14.10 + 3.23	23.33 + 4.41	22.13 + 4.68
Patient	12.20 + 2.77	19.50 + 3.58	18.48 + 3.94
Total organizational excellence	79.27+ 18.1 (Un-satisfactory)	124.4+ 22.4 (satisfactory)	117.7 + 24.1 (satisfactory)

Table (2) Arrays that, the distribution of the nursing managers satisfactory levels regarding organizational excellence in their work, which the highest mean and stander deviation in pre-test related to “nurses” (14.33 + 3.41), while the lowest mean and stander deviation was related to “Partnerships” (11.77 + 2.98), and the total mean and stander deviation was (79.27+ 18.1), which considered as unsatisfactory level, as compared with the phase of post-test the highest mean and stander deviation related to “nurses” (23.35 + 4.09), while the lowest mean and stander deviation was related to “Partnerships” (19.38 + 3.66), and the total mean and stander deviation was (124.4+ 22.4) considered as satisfactory level, Additionally, during the phase of follow (3 months after program) the highest mean and stander deviation related to “Processes”

(22.13 + 4.68), while the lowest mean and stander deviation was related to “Policy and strategy” (18.35 + 3.81), and the total mean and stander deviation was (117.7 + 24.1) considered as satisfactory level.

DISCUSSION

Considering personal characteristics of the sample of the study (nursing managers), the study result showed that about two thirds of the age range of the nursing managers was more than forty-one years old, with a high mean age. This indicated that the nursing managers were mature enough and able to tolerate the work responsibility. In relation to gender, majority of them were female. From the researcher point of view, this may be due to the greater fraction of the nurses in Egypt was female and may also related to the studying of nursing in Egyptian universities were exclusive for females only till few years ago.

Additionally, most of the nursing managers hold a bachelor's nursing degrees. This may indicate that nurses with a bachelor nursing degree were promoted to a higher position. Considering years of experience, most of them worked equal or more than eleven years in nursing profession. Regarding the total tenure time as nurse manager, more than two forth of them worked equal or more than eleven years. This explains that most of those nursing managers were adults and tolerated the nature of the work.

On the same line, the study finding was in a harmony with a quasi-experimental study result conducted at Benha University Hospital Qaluobia Governate, Egypt by **Abdel Azem et al., (2021)** which reviewed effect of educational program about talent management for nursing managers on their job affiliation and organizational excellence, showed that half of the nursing managers their age was ranged from forty five to less than fifty five years old with mean age (34.58±6.49). Additionally, majority of them were female, more than two thirds had bachelor’s degree, more than half having years of experience from ten to less than twenty years with mean years of experience (16.23±5.36). Moreover, most of them work as head nurses.

Regarding this concept and considering the total knowledge regarding organizational excellent during pre, post & three months follow up among the nursing managers. The study result denoted that, during the post-test phase, the nursing managers gained higher percentage of a satisfactory level of knowledge regarding organizational excellent followed by the phase of follow-up test as compared with the phase of pre-test that involved the lower percentage. In addition to the presence of a highly statistically significant difference. It means that the educational program has an effect on improving knowledge regarding organizational excellence among the nursing managers.

On the line, the study finding was in a harmony with a quasi-experimental study result conducted at Benha University Hospital Qaluobia Governate, Egypt by **Abdel Azem Mostafa et al., (2021)** which reviewed effect of educational program about talent management for nursing managers on their job affiliation and organizational excellence, showed that there was statistical general improvement in total level of nursing managers' organizational excellence post and follow- up as compared to pre-program.

CONCLUSION

The current study explores the effect of enhancing nursing managers organizational excellence educational program and found during the pre-test the studied nursing managers gained (17.5%). As compared with the phase of post-test phase nursing managers gained satisfactory level of knowledge regarding organizational excellent with the (87.5%) than the following phase they gained (85%) in the follow-up test.

Recommendations

Based on the study finding, the following recommendations are suggested in order to promote organizational excellence to improve competences level of nursing managers.

- To achieve an organizational Excellence, every nurse manager must understand not only the company's vision, but also know their own roles, responsibilities and the specific actions they need to take in order to help achieve this vision.
- Nursing managers must create highly collaborative teams , A key characteristic of an organizational excellence is highly collaborative teams.

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